

Digital image based finite element analysis of the material properties of foam

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SUMMARY: X-ray microtomography is used to acquire an accurate description of the interior microstructure of cellular materials. The data obtained from the X-ray microtomographic investigation is used as input to a programmed mesh algorithm which converts voxels directly into eight-node brick finite elements. From the generated model the effective stiffness properties of a cube of aluminium foam is determined from the volumetrically averaged stresses and strains.

KEYWORDS: X-ray microtomography, Finite element analysis, Effective elastic properties, Cellular materials

INTRODUCTION

The use of cellular materials, or foams, has over the last decade or so become more and more common in structural applications such as sandwich panels for boats, aircraft and aerospace components. This is due to the high stiffness-to-weight ratio of the foam materials which is desirable in structures where the weight is a critical design factor. To exploit the potential of the cellular materials, exact knowledge of the effective mechanical properties is essential. The microstructure of cellular materials consists of closely packed cells and are normally classified as either open or closed cell foams but in practice most foams consist of both types of cells. The microstructure is therefore described by a very complex geometry which renders modelling of the effective mechanical properties very complicated. In mathematical models this can be dealt with by assuming a simplified and repeated microstructure and describing the microstructure using macroscopic properties like the relative density.

Over the years, several attempts to predict the effective properties of cellular materials have been performed and a large amount of literature can be found on this topic. Gibson and Ashby [1] considered various aspects of both open and closed cell materials, based on unit cells and micromechanical considerations and this is probably one of the most well-known approaches. Another class of methods used in the modelling of the effective properties of cellular materials is continuum mechanical approaches known from composite mechanics. The methods in this class have varying sophistication and the most simple are probably the Voigt and Reuss approximations which give the upper and lower limits respectively of the true effective elastic moduli. To get a more accurate determination of the effective properties more sophisticated models like the composite spheres model, the generalized self-consistent method (GSCM), the three-phase model (TPM) and the Mori-Tanaka approach have been proposed. Another way to determine the effective properties is by use of variational bounding in which statistical information on the microstructure is incorporated through N -point correlation functions. The two-point correlation function represents e.g. the probability that two points a distance r apart belongs to the solid phase. The accuracy of the variational bounds may be improved by incorporating additional statistical information. However, in practice it is very difficult to determine correlation functions above the third order. A more thorough description of the different approaches can be found in [2-5].

The effective properties of a cellular material are highly dependent on cell size and cell shape and for a general interpenetrating porous media the accuracy of the models described is not known [6]. Consequently, numerical methods like the finite element method are needed in the analysis of the effective mechanical properties. Furthermore, the finite element method can be used to examine the deformation mechanisms in the cellular material and information about the stress and strain levels

locally in the microstructure can be obtained. For different simplified cell geometries the finite element method has been used to investigate how the properties are influenced by a non-periodic microstructure, cell shape and imperfections like cell wall curvature and corrugations [7-11]. The finite element method has also been used to analyse more complex geometries by Roberts and Garboczi [12-14] where statistical models are used to generate the cellular microstructures. Real microstructures have been modelled by e.g. Ladd and Kinney [15] and Nieh et al. [16] where the microstructure is imaged and lattice models are generated from the images. Generally it was found that the properties of the cellular materials are highly dependent on the microstructure. In this paper the actual microstructure of the cellular material is obtained using X-ray microtomography and from the obtained data finite element models are generated and analysed with the objective of finding the effective mechanical properties of the material.

DETERMINATION OF THE MATERIAL MICROSTRUCTURE

The morphological characterization of material microstructures has been improved by recent innovations in the field of X-ray attenuation measurement on small volume elements [17]. By employing the X-ray microtomographic technique on the cellular materials, images of the interior can be obtained in a non-destructive way. The X-ray microtomographic scanner used is the commercially available high-resolution SkyScan 1072 system. The scanner is equipped with an X-ray source working in the energy range 20-100 keV, a detector that consists of a 1024×1024 12-bit cooled CCD camera and the maximum resolution of the equipment is approximately $5\mu\text{m}$. For in-situ compression and tension tests, the microtomograph is equipped with a custom-made deformation rig, described in [18]. The SkyScan equipment and the deformation rig are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The SkyScan 1072 system used in this work (left) and the in-situ deformation rig (right).

The specimen to be investigated is placed between an X-ray source and a detector and in the simplest case, parallel X-ray beams illuminate the specimen. The attenuation of the X-rays, after passing through the specimen is measured by the detector. The object is rotated $180^\circ/360^\circ$ in the same plane and attenuation measurements are collected from a number of different viewpoints. From the attenuation measurements a two-dimensional image of a cross section in the object can be reconstructed as a map of the attenuated X-ray in the sample. The principle of computerized microtomography is shown in Fig. 2. A detailed description of the X-ray microtomographic technique can be found in e.g. [19, 20].

Figure 2: The principle of X-ray microtomographic measurements

From a set of cross section images, a full three-dimensional reconstruction of the microstructure can be made by stacking these images.

FROM TWO-DIMENSIONAL CROSS SECTIONS TO THREE-DIMENSIONAL STRUCTURE

The data obtained from any object investigated using the X-ray microtomographic technique is presented as a set of bitmap images where all images are well positioned with respect to each other. At the maximum resolution the images contain 1024×1024 pixels and the number of cross sections is determined from the resolution of the CCD and the selected area of interest from the shadow image. The maximum number of cross sections in a full three-dimensional reconstruction is 1024. This means that the microstructure is described by a maximum of 10^9 voxels with distinct color information where the color is related to the density at that point of the microstructure. The pixel dimensions and the distance between individual cross sections define the spatial location of each voxel. In a data set, all pixels have the same dimensions and the cross sections are equally spaced. Furthermore, the dimensions of the pixels and the cross sectional distance are well defined and an accurate description of the microstructure can therefore be obtained.

Different approaches can be used when performing the three-dimensional reconstruction and mesh generation from the two-dimensional images obtained from the microtomographic investigation. One approach is to create a smooth three-dimensional surface representation of the microstructure using edge detection techniques on the images. The obtained surface presentation can then be used as input to a meshing procedure whereby a mesh with a smooth surface is obtained. Generating the mesh this way provides a good mesh but is very time consuming due to the very complex geometry [21].

Another approach is the voxel conversion technique in which the voxel data is converted directly into a finite element mesh by converting each voxel directly into an eight-node brick element. Hereby the three-dimensional reconstruction and mesh generation are performed in a single step and so this approach is much faster. Additionally, the obtained finite element mesh is completely structured and all elements are identical, which is convenient when solving the finite element problem as described later. A disadvantage of the voxel conversion technique is that the mesh will have a stair-stepped surface introducing stress and strain concentrations at surface points. In this work the voxel conversion technique is used for the three-dimensional reconstruction and mesh generation.

An algorithm that uses the two-dimensional images as input for the three-dimensional reconstruction and mesh generation has been programmed and is described in the following. The algorithm consists of two parts, an image processing part and a mesh generation part and has been programmed in Fortran 90. The images obtained from the X-ray tomographic investigations are in grey-scale, Fig. 3a, where black represents non-material. The first operation performed on the images is a smoothing

using a 5×5 spatial lowpass filter to reduce the noise in the images. After the smoothing operation a thresholding is performed to get black and white images and thereby an unambiguous separation of material and non-material. The threshold value used for the thresholding is determined as an average of all non-black pixels in the first image in the data set and this value is used for all the images. The last operation performed in the image processing part of the program is an erosion. Thereby extraneous pixels are removed and a smoother border between material and non-material is obtained. The result of the image processing is shown for a single cross section in Fig. 3b.

Figure 3: Cross section of aluminium foam; (a) obtained from the X-ray microtomograph and (b) same image after the image processing. The resolution of both images is 512×512 pixels.

After the image processing the three-dimensional reconstruction and mesh generation is performed. In the mesh generation process it is utilized that the origin of the x- and y-axis is shared by all cross section images. This means that all pixels in a cross section can be assigned a unique number and furthermore pixels with the same x- and y-coordinates will have the same number in all cross sections. By comparing pixel n to pixel n in the cross section above it is determined if a voxel represents material or non-material. The voxel is defined as material and converted to an eight-node brick element if both pixels are white and if not then the voxel is defined as non-material. The reason for using this strategy is that small groups of white pixels may be found in some of the images and the resulting elements will not be connected to the rest of the microstructure. The material properties of each element are assigned from the color of the pixels defining the voxels. The mesh algorithm is therefore not limited to cellular materials but can be used for any composite material investigated in the X-ray microtomograph.

To get a proper description of the material microstructure a minimum number of elements is needed to describe the geometry of the individual struts and walls in the cellular material. To ensure a sufficient number of elements in all parts of the microstructure the magnification therefore has to be chosen from the smallest dimension in the material. The stair-stepped surface representation introduces stress and strain concentrations and the values determined at surface points will therefore be too high influencing the values at interior points. This influence may also be reduced if a sufficient number of elements is present in the struts/walls. The accuracy of the generated geometry and the determined stress and strain distributions are therefore very dependent on the magnification used in the X-ray microtomographic investigation

SOLUTION OF THE FINITE ELEMENT PROBLEM AND DETERMINATION OF THE EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES

When solving the finite element problem the following system of linear equations has to be solved:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

in which \mathbf{K} is the global stiffness matrix, \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector and \mathbf{f} the external force vector. The finite element code used in this work is MUST which has been developed at Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Aalborg University and the method described in the following has been implemented in this FE code.

The models generated for the cellular microstructure may contain millions of elements making the system of equations in (1) very large and due to the amount of memory needed to store \mathbf{K} , the problem cannot be solved using direct solvers. Instead the problem is solved iteratively using the preconditioned conjugate gradient (PCG) algorithm, shown in eq. (2), with an element-by-element (EBE) preconditioner, \mathbf{M} , which is very efficient in combination with the PCG solver [22].

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{x}_{(0)} = \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{r}_{(0)} = \mathbf{f}, \text{ solve } \mathbf{M}\mathbf{z}_{(0)} = \mathbf{r}_{(0)} \\ & \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots \text{ convergence do} \\ & \quad \beta_{(i)} = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{(i-1)}^T \mathbf{r}_{(i-1)}}{\mathbf{z}_{(i-1)}^T \mathbf{r}_{(i-2)}} \quad \beta_{(1)} = 0 \\ & \quad \mathbf{p}_{(i)} = \mathbf{z}_{(i-1)} + \beta_{(i)} \mathbf{p}_{(i-1)} \quad \mathbf{p}_{(1)} = \mathbf{z}_{(0)} \\ & \quad \alpha_{(i)} = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{(i-1)}^T \mathbf{r}_{(i-1)}}{\mathbf{p}_{(i)}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{p}_{(i)}} \\ & \quad \mathbf{x}_{(i)} = \mathbf{x}_{(i-1)} + \alpha_{(i)} \mathbf{p}_{(i)} \\ & \quad \mathbf{r}_{(i)} = \mathbf{r}_{(i-1)} + \alpha_{(i)} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{p}_{(i)} \quad \text{check convergence} \\ & \quad \text{solve } \mathbf{M}\mathbf{z}_{(i)} = \mathbf{r}_{(i)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The EBE preconditioners are a specialized class of preconditioners well suited for analysis of large problems where the finite element problem is solved at element level. In that way it is avoided to assemble and store the global stiffness matrix, which greatly reduces memory usage. In the present models generated from the digital images all elements are the same why only a single element stiffness matrix needs to be stored, allowing us to store and solve very large problems on a standard PC. A number of different EBE preconditioners have been developed and described in e.g. [23]. The EBE preconditioners are all based on similar principles namely a normalization followed by a regularization and a factorization. The EBE preconditioner used in this work is the Crout preconditioner, which is based on diagonal scaling, Winget regularization and finally a Crout (or Cholesky) factorization. The Winget regularization ensures that the diagonally scaled element stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_e is positive-definite and hence the Crout factorization is well defined. The Winget regularization is given as

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}_e = \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{D}^{-1/2} (\mathbf{K}_e - \mathbf{D}_e) \mathbf{D}^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{K})$ and $\mathbf{D}_e = \text{diag}(\mathbf{K}_e)$. A Crout factorization of the regularized element stiffness matrix is performed

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \mathbf{L}_e \mathbf{D}_e \mathbf{L}_e^T \quad (4)$$

and the preconditioner is given by the following product decomposition

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{D}^{1/2} \times \prod_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{L}_e \times \prod_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{D}_e \times \prod_{e=N_{el}}^1 \mathbf{L}_e^T \times \mathbf{D}^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where N_{el} is the number of elements in the finite element mesh. The last product in eq. (5) is in reverse order of the first one, which results in \mathbf{M} being symmetric. Performing the preconditioning therefore consists of a sequence of forward reductions and back substitutions on element matrices, which is very efficient.

The stresses and strains obtained from the finite element analysis are volumetric averaged and used for the determination of the effective properties of the cellular material. The volumetric averaged stresses and strains are respectively defined as

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma_{ij} dV = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \sigma_{ij}^e V^e \quad (6)$$

and

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \epsilon_{ij} dV = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \epsilon_{ij}^e V^e \quad (7)$$

where V is the volume and the superscript e denotes the element stress, strain and volume. Inserting the averaged stresses and strains in Hooke's law gives

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \mathbf{C}_{ijkl}^{eff} \bar{\epsilon}_{kl} \quad (8)$$

where the averaged stresses is related to the averaged strains by the effective elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{C}_{ijkl}^{eff} .

To determine the 36 unknowns in the effective elastic stiffness tensor, for an anisotropic material, six analyses have to be performed. The analyses that have to be performed are three tension tests and three shear tests. In all cases a displacement is prescribed to all nodes on one surface and on the opposite surface one node is clamped and the rest are simply supported in the direction of the prescribed displacement.

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM FOAM

An open cell aluminium foam made of the 6101 T6 alloy with 40 PPI and a relative density of 0.07, provided by ERG Materials and Aerospace, has been examined. A cube of $10 \times 10 \times 13$ mm was cut using electronic discharge machining and examined in the X-ray microtomograph with a resolution of $27.137 \mu\text{m}$ per pixel and the same cross sectional distance. The cross sectional images of the microstructure were acquired at 67 KeV and $90 \mu\text{A}$ with an exposure time of 4.0 seconds by rotating in steps of 0.45° from 0 to 180° . The complete set of data from the X-ray microtomographic examination contained 343 images with a resolution of 512×512 pixels. Images containing 256×256 pixels were extracted from the original images to reduce the number of elements in the model. From the extracted images, a cube of $6.9 \times 6.9 \times 7.2$ mm was meshed using 270 cross sectional images, the mesh is shown in Fig. 4. The model contains 1,003,169 elements and 1,318,171 nodes giving nearly 4 million equations in eq. (1). The relative density of the generated model is determined to 0.064 which is 9.4% lower than the relative density given by ERG Materials and Aerospace. Due to the small difference in the relative densities the model is assumed to be fairly accurate representation of the original foam.

In the analyses all elements are isotropic and the bulk properties of the 6101 T6 aluminium alloy is used in the analyses and taken to be $E = 70,000$ MPa and $\nu = 0.33$. From the six analyses performed, the effective elastic stiffness tensor is determined and the symmetry corresponds to an isotropic material with a Young's modulus, E , of 3939 MPa. To get some validation of the obtained result, E is determined using the Voigt approximation giving the upper bound. Using the volume fractions from the generated finite element model the Voigt approximation predicts an effective modulus of 4200 MPa. The modulus determined from the finite element analyses therefore seems reasonable.

Besides the effective properties the finite element analyses also give detailed information on the stress and strain distributions and the deformations of the individual components in the microstructure. This information can be used to obtain better knowledge of the different deformation mechanisms in the material under loading.

Figure 4: Three-dimensional finite element mesh of aluminium foam. The model contains approximately 1 million elements and 270 cross sectional images with a resolution of 256×256 pixels where used for the mesh generation

A number of things influences the results obtained from the finite element analyses such as the number of cells included in the finite element model and the way the boundary conditions are applied. Furthermore, the resolution used in the X-ray microtomographic examination of the microstructure influences the accuracy of the generated models. To minimize the errors introduced from these their influence on the obtained results has to be examined.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It has been shown that X-ray microtomography can be used to obtain detailed information on the interior microstructure of cellular materials. From the obtained data, a three-dimensional finite element model is generated using the voxel conversion technique. The generated models contain a large number of elements and the problems are solved on element basis using the PCG solver with a Crout EBE preconditioner. The effective properties are determined using the volumetrically averaged stresses and strains and for the example used, the determined properties seem to be reasonable. For a further validation of the described method analyses have to be performed on other foam materials but

also on general composite materials. To determine the accuracy of the determined properties they have to be compared to results obtained with more sophisticated models than the Voigt approximation.

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